

Adequacy of Context and Input Evaluation of Agricultural Education Programme for Improved Hands-on Experience among Students in Tertiary Institutions in Rivers State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study evaluated the adequacy of context and input of agricultural education programme for improved hands-on experience among students of tertiary institutions in Rivers State. Two specific purposes, two research questions and two hypotheses were posed to guide the study. Evaluation research using quantitative approach was adopted for the study. The model adopted was CIPP model; which requires the assessment of context, input, process and product of agricultural education programme. Population and sample of the study consisted of 24 agricultural educators and 214 agricultural education undergraduate students from the three tertiary institutions offering agricultural education programme in Rivers State during the 2020/2021 academic session. Two instruments namely observational checklist and a questionnaire were developed by the researcher. The face validity of the instruments was determined by three experts, one expert of Educational Measurement and Evaluation, and two expert of Agricultural Education Department of Rivers State University, Port-Harcourt. Cronbach Alpha computed using Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) gave the following reliability index of 0.78 and 0.89 for the two clusters of the questionnaire. Data were analyzed using percentage, ratio, mean and standard deviation to answer research questions. Hypotheses is tested using Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) and independent sample t-test. The study revealed that the context of agricultural education for improved hands-on experience amongst students of tertiary institutions in Rivers State is adequate. The study also revealed inadequate non-human input resources for agricultural education for improved hands-on experiences amongst students of tertiary institutions in Rivers State. of tertiary institutions in Rivers State. Based on the findings, it was recommended among others that Federal and Rivers State government should provide more funding for the provision of adequate and functional input resources relating to instructional technology, infrastructure, equipment and consumables for agricultural education hands-on experiences amongst students of tertiary institutions in Rivers State.

Keyword: Context, Input, Evaluation, Agricultural Education Programme, Improved, Hands-on Experience

INTRODUCTION

Agricultural education offered at the tertiary education level which is the main focus of this study has been defined by different authors over the years. According to Alawa (2015), tertiary education agricultural education and training is meant to develop the human capital needed to sustain the operations of all levels of agricultural education and practices. Phipps, Osborne, Dyer and Ball (2010) noted that generally agricultural education is meant to inform the public about food production and agricultural practices for food security. Jessy and Charu (2015) opined that agricultural education utilizes broad field curriculum designed to develop students' capacity and make them more effective, self-reliant, resourceful, and capable of solving agricultural problems from their youthful age. Egun and Egun (2015) described agricultural education as the type of education that involves the process of acquiring practical skills and competencies which the recipients can ultimately transfer to agricultural job opportunities available in their immediate society. Olaitan (2017) noted that agricultural education is designed to enable its recipients develop knowledge and skills for the advancement of agricultural practices and for participating in functional agricultural sector. The definitions so far revealed that the essence of agricultural education is to equip learners with knowledge and skills for taking up careers within the agricultural sector of their economy in order to ensure food sufficiency and

increase wealth generation. Consequently, to achieve this, goals and objectives are outlined and curriculum is designed with content capable of leading to the attainment of the predetermined goals and objectives.

According to the National Policy on Education (Federal Republic of Nigeria, FRN, 2013), the objectives of vocational agricultural education are to help the recipients of the programme to develop skills, scientific knowledge and competencies required in agricultural sector; to develop in them an understanding and appreciation of career opportunities in the agricultural sector; to develop in them the ability to secure satisfaction in the placement and advancement in agricultural occupation through continuing education programmes; to develop in them leadership qualities, attitudes for co-operations, citizenship and patriotism by participating in experiences and activities of agricultural programmes; to develop in them competencies required by individuals engaged in agriculture; and to develop practical skills and competences in agricultural research. Evidences in literature also suggested that the main objectives of agricultural education in Nigeria is to provide the youth with sound knowledge of the basic principles and techniques of agriculture and the motivation to translate such knowledge into reality for the improvement of agricultural products (Ibrahim, 2014). Cajethan and Benardine (2015) noted that the main objective of agricultural education programme is to enhance and/or improve the traditional agricultural practices by concentrating on training recipients in essential knowledge and skills relating to crop farming, snail rearing, poultry farming, farm management techniques, goat farming among others which are very crucial for a successful career in agriculture. It is important to note that the attainment of these laudable objectives rest upon so many factors that focus on the curriculum content of agricultural education and its effective implementation at all level of the Nigerian educational system.

The curriculum content of agricultural education contains all the knowledge, skills and experiences which recipients are expected to acquire before being certified as graduates of the programme. Curriculum could be typically described as the total knowledge and skills students are expected to learn and it covers the learning objectives, the units and lessons that teachers are expected on the minimum to implement, the materials to be used and the various mode of evaluation to be taken in actualizing the programme objectives. National Future Farmers Association (National FFA, 2013) noted that a complete agricultural education curriculum has three main parts, that is, classroom/laboratory instruction, Future Farmers Association (FFA), and Supervised Agricultural Experience (SAE). National Council for Agricultural Education (2021) also noted that every agricultural education curriculum should provide students with the opportunities for leadership development, personal growth and career success

Hands-on experience requires the immersion of students in their own learning activities in order to have a first-hand experience of actions and challenges to performing them. According to Ekwueme, Meremikwu and Uka (2012), hands-on experience is used to engross learner in a total learning experience which enhances the ability to think critically. Tile (2013) described hands-on experience as learning situation where by the learner uses his/her hands to carry on concrete learning activities capable of enhancing the learner's knowledge, skills and experiences. Tile noted that concrete learning activities can include learning using apparatus or objects for measuring, weighting, demonstrating, carrying out tests/experiments and any other concrete activities that could enhance students' learning experience. Oludipe, Ojediran and Kareem (2020) noted that hands-on experience is student-centred approach that allows them to see, touch and manipulate objects while learning. From the discourse so far, it can be concluded that supporters of hands-on experience believed that students would learn better if they are engaged with the learning activities rather than with the awareness of the activities. This is based on the fact that it would provide them opportunity to experience the actual process of carrying out such activities in real life situations.

It is worth noting that agricultural development, for which formal agricultural education was initiated across the world, is actually an activity-based tasks, hence learning it also requires exposure to a wide range of hands-on agricultural tasks. Musa (2015) noted that it is in order to expose recipients of agricultural education to experiences that Supervised Agricultural Experience Activities and/or Projects (SAEP) were made component the programme in Nigeria. Famiwole (2015) also noted that supervised Agricultural Experience Programme are designed to develop students' entrepreneurial qualities through the process of starting, running and managing small or medium scale agricultural

project, under the supervision of an adviser, subject teacher, professionals and sometimes parents. Famiwole also noted that SAEP is meant to complement the classroom instructions and ensure skill development through real life agricultural projects on the field. However, a situation where many educators are said to be avoiding the use of hands-on experiences in empowering their students against the realities in the world of work calls for questionnaire the effectiveness with which the programme is being implemented to attain its objectives (Ekwueme & Meremikwu, 2010; Abdulkarim & Nwokocha, 2012; Remi & Kolawole, 2013). Consequently, it is not surprising that Remi and Kolawole (2013) found stakeholders (teachers and students) in agricultural education to be calling for the evaluation of the programme in order to appraise its effectiveness in helping students to develop the competencies needed to achieve their occupational objectives in Nigeria.

The context of an educational programme has to do with the objectives which it sets out to achieve because these in real sense should address the needs of the recipients and their immediate environment. Johnson and Walter (2012) opined that context evaluation is concern with needs assessment, and it is used in making program planning decisions. Ramsey and Edwards (2011) opined that context evaluation is used to assess participant needs for a programme or innovation in agricultural education. The programme curriculum is mostly the documents designed for the purpose of achieving the goals and objectives of any educational programme.

Curriculum is typically described as the total knowledge and skills students are expected to learn and it covers the learning objectives, the units and lessons that teachers teach the materials to be used and the various mode of evaluation to be taken in actualizing the programme objectives. A complete agricultural educational program curriculum according to the National Future Farmers Association (National FFA, 2013) should integrate three main parts, that is, classroom/laboratory instruction, Future Farmers Association (FFA), and Supervised Agricultural Experience (SAE) in order to always address the needs to the recipients. The association noted that motto of the FFA component of agricultural education is “Learning to Do, Doing to Learn, Earning to Live, and Living to Serve”. Olaitan (2010) opined that both the theoretical and practical aspects of agricultural education curriculum must be implemented together for the programme to be effective as intended. Consequently, in classroom learning is not sufficient for an effective agricultural education aimed to develop the recipients for leadership and for employment without field real life practical. National Council for Agricultural Education (2021) noted every agricultural education should provide students with the opportunities for leadership development, personal growth and career success.

Musa (2015) noted that the framework of vocational agricultural education curriculum for productive work skills development covers Supervised Agricultural Experience Activities and/or Projects (SAEP). Musa noted that the development of skills through exposure to agricultural experiences is meant to empower graduates to engage in their own agricultural businesses and enable them develop skills for teaching others improved agricultural practices. Stephen (2017) opined that SAEP can take the form of placement experiences in farm and off-farm agribusiness settings which if coupled with laboratory experiences, exploratory experiences and research-based experiences would equip students to be self-efficacious in agricultural ventures.

Remi and Kolawole (2013) also noted that agricultural education at the tertiary institution is mostly implemented without exposing students to Supervised Agricultural Experience Programme (SAEP) related to subject contents which is a basic requirement. Ekezie and Owo (2019) found that the stakeholders in agricultural education are of the view that the curriculum content at the university level is adequate enough to train students in vocational agricultural skills development. Consequently, the graduating students lack the knowledge, skills and confidence to practice agricultural ventures after graduation. In the context of this work, context evaluation is seen as the process of assessing the objectives of agricultural education hands-on experiences which are sets out to address the needs of the recipients of the programme and the assessment of the curriculum content which are designed for implementation in order to achieve the programme’s objectives.

Inputs resources for agricultural education programme are meant to enhance the attainment of the programme objectives by ensuring effective implementation of the curriculum content as well as to facilitate students’ learning, retention, competencies and productivity. According to Lincoln (2009), inputs are materials and resources required for the proper and effective execution of a given task. Right to Education (2021) also defined inputs in any educational

programme as things that are required in order to achieve predetermined education objectives, and they include: the number of lecturers, school facilities and teaching aids, and the cost and level of financial resources to be used. For agricultural education, input resources apart from human resources include agricultural laboratory, agricultural workshop tank, tractors, cultivators, combined harvester, school farm, a departmental vehicle and funds for running the department (Konyango & Asienyo, 2015). Cheplogoi (2011) noted that input resources in agricultural education are instructional resources and basically, they can be linked to the programme's curriculum and syllabus since they are provided to ensure their effective implementation as well as a practical. Amadi (2011) opined that instructional resources are all materials and equipment used to enhance effective learning of agricultural education curriculum content.

Kalu (2012) noted that the human resource component interacts with other input resources in order to drive the attainment of the desired output, hence the quality of educational programme output is to a greater extent dependent on the quality and quantity of input resource and how they interact in the process of delivery the output. Otu, Etok, and Asikpo (2018) opined that there is need to change youth attitude towards farming through the development of their competence in agricultural acts which can only ensure via the tutelage of competent instructors and use of adequate instructional materials procured on good funding. EDULINK Project (2019) outlined certain agricultural education courses facilities that need to be provided in tertiary institutions if the curriculum implementation is to produce the caliber of graduates that would drive agricultural enterprise revolution. The facilities outlined include laboratory facilities, field research facilities, machinery and farm equipment, highly trained technicians and teaching staff with entrepreneurial competence, library and other information resources, teaching and research farms, animals' resources center, computers and software for demonstration and analysis.

The essence of input resources in running and achieving the predetermine goal of any educational programmes in tertiary institutions in Nigeria cannot be overemphasized. According to Francis, Charles and Vincent (2020), in Nigeria, National Universities Commission (NUC), National Board for Technical Education (NBTE) and National Commission for Colleges of Education (NCCE) are central established institutions charged with the responsibility to determine the minimum input requirements for any academic programme. Francis, Charles and Vincent (2020) noted that these institutions prescribe minimum human resources, structures, infrastructures, equipment and associated facilities in the benchmark minimum academic standards (BMAS) for each accredited educational programme.

In agricultural education, the minimum input requirements for different tertiary institutions vary based on their supervisory agency BMAS. For agricultural education offered at the universities, NUC specifies the minimum input requires while for Colleges of Education, NCCE has the mandate to establish the input resources. In general, the input resources are academic human resources to student ratio of 1:30, technology, equipment and all consumables ratio to student of 1:3 (Federal Republic of Nigeria, FRN, 2018). Resources for the implementation of Agricultural Education programme according to the National Commission for Colleges of Education (NCCE, 2020) can be categorised into human, physical, information and financial resources. NCCE noted that physical resources include space or land, buildings, equipment, furniture and so on; human resource refers to teaching, support and administrative staff; information resource as print and non-print media, while financial resource refers to cost of non-recurring and recurring expenditures on the institution as a system. The Commission stipulated physical resources such as classrooms, laboratories, school farms, book in the library, other facilities such as tractor with the necessary coupling implement and haulage vehicles for transportation, equipment, tools and materials; while it defined support staff to consists of technologists, technicians, artisans and labour hand that include maximum of two messengers; academic staff to students ratio for agricultural education programme is also fixed at 1:25 students (NCCE, 2020).

Statement of the Problem

The preliminary investigation by the researcher revealed that the graduates of agricultural education from most tertiary institutions in Rivers State find it difficult to demonstrate their skills in most of the stated skilled areas. This situation has seen most of the graduates joining the unemployed population of the State rather than being self-employed and even being creator of agricultural jobs. Consequently, the graduates become bedeviled with psychological problems

of being incapable to earn a living from decent agricultural ventures. These situations are disturbing and naturally call for questioning if agricultural education hands-on experiences programmes such as supervised agricultural experiences and future farmers association were properly implemented or the appropriateness of the objectives and goals of the programmes or if the programmes were implemented using the appropriate content and adequate input resources. These call for the evaluation of the entire system within which the programmes operate in order to see whether there is need for improvement. It is for these reasons that the present study is being conducted.

Purpose of the study

The main purpose of the study is to evaluate agricultural education programme for improved hands-on experience amongst tertiary education students in Rivers State. Specifically, the study seeks to:

1. Determine the adequacy of context of agricultural education programme for improved hands-on experience among students of tertiary institutions in Rivers State.
2. Determine the adequacy of inputs necessary for implementing agricultural education programme for improved hands-on experience among students of tertiary institutions in Rivers State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

- i. What is the adequacy of context of agricultural education programme for improved hands-on experience among students of tertiary institutions in Rivers State?
- ii. What is adequacy of inputs necessary for implementing agricultural education programme for improved hands-on experience among students of tertiary institutions in Rivers State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

1. There is no significant difference in the mean rating of agricultural educators from Rivers State University, Ignatius Ajuru University of Education and Federal College of Education (Tech.), Omoku on the adequacy of context of agricultural education programme for improved hands-on experience among students of Tertiary institutions in Rivers State.
2. There is no significant difference in the adequacy of inputs necessary for implementing agricultural education programme hands-on experience among students of tertiary institutions in Rivers State.

METHODOLOGY

This study adopted evaluation research design. Consequently, this evaluation research design is based on the Stufflebeam's CIPP model. This model was used to assess and make quantitative judgment about the context and input of agricultural education for improved hands-on experiences in tertiary institutions in Rivers State. This model is deemed appropriate since it allows the researcher to evaluate the various elements of agricultural education programme for hands-on experience. The area of this study is Rivers State of Nigeria. The population of this study is made up 24 agricultural education lecturers in tertiary institutions in Rivers State.

Table 1: Population of the Study

Name of Institutions	Lecturers
Rivers State University, Port-Harcourt	5
Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Port-Harcourt	5
Federal College of Education (Tech.), Omoku	14
Total	24

Source: Heads of Agricultural Education Departments

The entire population of the study was used for the study. This is because it is manageable. Therefore, no sampling technique was used in this study. The instruments for data collection in this study were made up of observational checklist and questionnaire. The two instruments were developed by the researcher based on the specifications in the BMAS for Agricultural Education from both the National University Commission (NUC) and from National

Commission for Colleges of Education (NCCE). The observational checklist is titled “Input Resources Evaluation Checklist for Agricultural Education Hands-on Experiences in Tertiary Institutions in Rivers State (IRECAEHETIR)”. The instrument was designed using Benchmark minimum Academic standard for undergraduate programmes in Nigeria Universities (2017) for on-site observation of the context and input resource for hands-on experience programme evaluation. The checklist contains 31 items. The responses pattern for the questionnaire is structured based on four-point rating scale options of Strongly Agreed (SA – 4 points), Agreed (A – 3 points), Disagreed (D – 2 points) and Strongly Disagreed (SD – 1 point).

The instruments were subjected to face-validation by three experts, one expert of Educational Measurement and Evaluation, and two experts of Agricultural Education Department of Rivers State University, Port-Harcourt. To determine the reliability of the instrument, Cronbach Alpha reliability index which gave 0.78, and 0.89 reliability index. The checklist was filled by the evaluator during on-site direct observation of the input resources of agricultural education for improved hands-on experience in tertiary institutions in Rivers State. Data generated from the checklist were analysed using frequency, percentage and ratio to answer the adequacy of input resources as stipulated in NUC and NCCE BMAS for agricultural education. The data generated from the closed items structured questionnaire was analyzed using mean and standard deviation scores. Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used to test hypotheses. To staff adequacy, staff to student ratio of 1:30 based on NUC BMAS and 1:25 based on NCCE BMAS was regarded as adequate and below this was regarded as inadequate; while the ratio of technology, equipment and consumables to student of 1:03 for both supervisory agencies, hence figure below this was regarded as inadequate. To answer research questions 1, mean of 3.5 above was regarded as Strongly Agreed, 2.5 to 3.49 was regarded as Agreed, 1.5 to 2.49 was regarded as Disagreed and below 1.5 was regarded as Strongly Disagreed. In testing the null hypotheses, the decision rule of ANOVA computed with SPSS was used to draw conclusion about the results. The acceptance rule states that where the p value obtained is greater than the p-value provided at 0.05, the null hypothesis be accepted; while, where the p-value obtained from the computation is less than or equal to the provided p value at 0.05, the null hypothesis be rejected (Kpolovie, 2011).

RESULT

Research Question 1: What is the adequacy of context of agricultural education programme for improved hands-on experience among students of tertiary institutions in Rivers State?

Table 1: Summary of Mean on the Adequacy of Context of Agricultural Education Programme for Improved Hands-on Experience among Students of Tertiary Institutions in Rivers State

S/N	Objectives items	RSU Lecturers n = 05		IAUOE Lecturers n = 05		FCE (T), Omoku Lecturers n=14	
		\bar{X}	Decision	\bar{X}	Decision	\bar{X}	Decision
1	To develop skills and have scientific knowledge and competencies required in agricultural sector;	3.20	Adequate	3.20	Adequate	3.14	Adequate
2	To develop the ability to secure satisfaction in the placement and advancement in agricultural occupation through programmes on continuing education;	3.40	Adequate	3.00	Adequate	3.21	Adequate
3	To develop leadership qualities, attitudes, thrifts scholarship co-operations, citizenship and patriotism by participating in experiences and activities of agricultural programmes;	2.80	Adequate	3.40	Adequate	3.14	Adequate
4	To develop competencies required by individuals engaged in agriculture	3.00	Adequate	3.40	Adequate	2.79	Adequate
5	To develop practical skills and competences in agricultural research.	3.20	Adequate	3.00	Adequate	3.21	Adequate

Mean	3.12	3.20	3.10
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Source: Field Survey, 2021

Table 1 evaluates the context of agricultural education for improved hands-on-experience by assessing whether the objectives stated for the programme can promote hands-on-experiences. The table shows that lecturers from RSU, IAUOE and FCE(T), Omoku all agreed that the objectives stated for agricultural education programme which are to develop skills and have scientific knowledge and competencies required in agricultural sector; to develop the ability to secure satisfaction in the placement and advancement in agricultural occupation through programmes on continuing education; to develop leadership qualities, attitudes, thrifts scholarship co-operations, citizenship and patriotism by participating in experiences and activities of agricultural programmes; to develop competencies required by individuals engaged in agriculture; and to develop practical skills and competences in agricultural research can promote hands-on-experiences with mean scores of 3.20, 3.20, 3.40, 3.40, 3.00, 3.21, 2.80, 3.40, 3.14, 3.00, 3.40, 2.79, 3.20, 3.00, and 3.21 respectively. In same vein, when the mean scores for all the items at 3.12, 3.20, and 3.10 are considered, it can be concluded that lecturers from RSU, IAUOE, and FCE (T.), Omoku all agreed to the adequacy of the context of agricultural education for improved hands-on experience amongst students of tertiary institutions in Rivers State.

Research Question 2: What is adequacy of inputs necessary for implementing agricultural education hands-on experience among students of tertiary institutions in Rivers State?

Table 2: Summary of Ratio and Percentage Analysis on the Adequacy of Inputs Necessary in Agricultural Education for Improved Hands-on-Experience among Students of Tertiary Institutions in Rivers State.

S/N	Human Resources	RSU			IAUOE			FCE(T.), OMOKU		
		Ratio	Percent	Decision	Ratio	Percent	Decision	Ratio	Percent	Decision
1.	Academic Staff	1:12	19%	Adequate	1:17	20%	Adequate	1:5	08%	Adequate
2.	Non-academic staff	1:6	10%	Adequate	1:10	12%	Adequate	1:8	12%	Adequate
S/N	Instructional Technology Appraisal									
3.	Computer systems	1:4	07%	Not adequate	1:09	11%	Not adequate	1:7	10%	Not adequate
4.	Internet Access	1:4	07%	Not adequate	0	0%	Not Available	0	0%	Not Available
5.	Agricultural education software	0	0%	Not available	0	0%	Not available	0	0%	Not Available
6.	Multimedia projector	1:62	100%	Not adequate	1:85	100%	Not adequate	1:67	100%	Not adequate
S/N	Infrastructure Appraisal									
7.	Classrooms	1:5	08%	Adequate	1:09	11%	Adequate	1:7	10%	Adequate
8	Lecture theatre	0	0%	Not available	1:85	100%	Adequate	0	0%	Not available
9	Demonstration Farm:	1:62	100%	Not adequate	1:85	100%	Not adequate	1:67	100%	Not adequate
	Greenhouse	0	0%	Not available	0	0%	Not available	0	0%	Not available
	Hutches	0	0%	Not available	0	0%	Not available	0	0%	Not available
	Ponds/Tanks	0	0%	Not available	1:85	100%	Not adequate	1:67	100%	Not adequate
	Domestic animal barns	1:62	100%	Not adequate	1:85	100%	Not adequate	1:67	100%	Not adequate

10	Laboratory: Experiment tools Microscope	1:62 1:12 1:62	100% 19% 100%	Not adequate Not adequate Not adequate	1:85 1:17 0	100% 20% 0%	Not adequate Not adequate Not available	1:67 1:13 0	100% 19% 0%	Not adequate Not adequate Not available
11	Library: Book shelves Current agricultural education practical textbooks Agricultural encyclopedia Seats Reading tables	1:62 1:12 1:31 1:62 1:4 1:31	100% 19% 50% 100% 07% 50%	Not adequate Not adequate Not adequate Not adequate Not adequate Not adequate	1:85 1:43 0 1:43 1:06 1:28	100% 49% 0% 49% 07% 33%	Not adequate Not adequate Not available Not adequate Not adequate Not adequate	1:67 1:5 1:2 1:34 1:3 1:4	100% 08% 63% 51% 37% 27%	Not adequate Not adequate adequate Not adequate adequate Not adequate
12	Staff office: Air-conditioner Seats Tables	1:0.6 1:0.6 1:1.54 1:1.54	12% 12% 30% 30%	Adequate Not adequate Adequate Adequate	1:02 1:04 1:01 1:01	40% 80% 20% 20%	Adequate Not adequate Adequate Adequate	1:2 1:4 1:2 1.1	56% 39% 50% 100%	Adequate Not adequate Adequate Adequate
S/N	Equipment Appraisal									
13	Farm tools	1:5	08%	Not adequate	1:12	14%	Not adequate	1:4	27%	Not adequate
14	Tractors	1:21	34%	Not adequate	1:85	100%	Not adequate	1:34	51%	Not adequate
15	Planting machine	1:31	50%	Not adequate	0	0%	Not available	0	0%	Not available
16	Harvesters	1:31	50%	Not adequate	0	0%	Not available	0	0%	Not available
17	Hutches machines	1:62	100%	Not adequate	0	0%	Not available	0	0%	Not available
18	Agricultural product drying machine	1:62	100%	Not adequate	0	0%	Not available	0	0%	Not available
19	Grinder	1:62	100%	Not adequate	0	0%	Not available	0	0%	Not available
20	Packaging tools	0	0%	Not available	0	0%	Not available	0	0%	Not available
S/N	Consumables Appraisal									
21	Seedlings	0	0%	Not available	0	0%	Not available	0	0%	Not available
22	Fingerlings	0	0%	Not available	0	0%	Not available	0	0%	Not available
23	Snails	0	0%	Not available	0	0%	Not available	0	0%	Not available
24	Domestic animals	0	0%	Not available	1:2	02%	Adequate	0	0%	Not available
25	Animal feeds	0	0%	Not available	1:85	100%	Not adequate	0	0%	Not available
26	Fish feeds	0	0%	Not available	0	0%	Not available	0	0%	Not available
27	Agricultural chemicals	0	0%	Not available	0	0%	Not available	0	0%	Not available
28	Organic fertilizer	0	0%	Not available	0	0%	Not available	0	0%	Not available
29	Non-organic fertilizer	0	0%	Not available	0	0%	Not available	0	0%	Not available
30	Birds	0	0%	Not available	1:03	28%	adequate	1:02	50%	Adequate
31	Funding	0	0%	Not available	0	0%	Not available	0	0%	Not available

Source: Field Survey, 2021

Table 2 shows that RSU has adequate human resources in agricultural education programme for improved hands-on-experiences with the ratio of academic staff at 1 lecturer to 12 undergraduates' students which means each lecturer can handle 19% of the students at a time; and the ratio of non-academic staff at 1 staff to 6 students which also translate to the fact that each non-academic staff can attend to 10% of the students at a time. The table also shows that in IAUOE a ratio of academic staff 1 lecturer to 17 students which means that each lecturer can handle 20% of the students at a time; while the ratio of non-academic staff is at 1 staff to 10 which also means that each can handle 12% of the students at a time. This means in IAUOE, there are adequate human resources in agricultural education programme for improved hands-on-experiences. The table also shows that in F.C.E. (T.), Omoku, there adequate human resources in agricultural education department for hands-on experiences because with a ratio of 1:05 for academic staff and 1:08 for non-academic staff, it means each academic staff would only have 8% of the entire students to handle at a time, while the non-academic staff would only attend to 12% of the students at a time. When all the ratios obtained from

the three institutions are compared with ratios given by NUCBMAS and NCCE BMAS of 1:30 and 1:25 respectively for human resources.

Table 2 also shows that RSU has a ratio of 1:04 computer systems which can be utilized to instruct 7% of the students at a time as against ratio 1:3 prescribed by NUCBMAS. It also shows that RSU provides access to internet at a ratio of 1:04 which can only serve 7% of the students at a time. RSU also has a ratio of 1:62 for multimedia projector provided for implementing agricultural education. Agricultural education software in RSU as input resource for agricultural education was not available. The ratios obtained for RSU reveal that the input resources computer systems and internet are inadequate. Table 2 also shows that IAUOE has ratio of 1:9 and 1:85 for computer systems and multimedia projector provided as input resources for agricultural education programme hands-on-experience which means that these instructional technologies can be used to handle 11% and 100% of the students at a time respectively. The analysis also shows that there is no internet access and agricultural education software for agricultural education students' hands-on experience in IAUOE. The table also shows that in F.C.E. (T.), Omoku computer system and media projector provided are in ratio of 1:7 and 1:67 which means they can be used to serve 10% and 100% of the students at a time. These ratios also show that these instructional technologies are inadequate when compared with NCCE BMAS which provides for 1:3 and 1:25 students. The results also show that in F.C.E. (T.), Omoku, agricultural education input resources such as internet and agricultural education software are not available for students' hands-on experiences.

Table 2 also shows that there are adequate classrooms in RSU, IAUOE and F.C.E. (T.), Omoku at the ratio of 1:5, 1:9, and 1:7 which means that the students would only occupy 08%, 11% and 10% of the classrooms respectively at a time. The analysis also shows IAUOE has adequate lecture theatre at a ratio of 1:85 which means it can contain the entire students at a time and is less than NUCBMAS standard of 100 students' capacity theatre. Table 2 also reveals that in RSU, IAUOE and F.C.E. (T.), Omoku there are adequate staff offices at a ratio of 1:0.6, 1:02 and 1:02 respectively. These translate to the fact that offices would accommodate 12%, 40%, and 56% of the staff respectively. The analysis also shows that the seat and table for the staff are adequate at the ratio 1:1.54, 1:01, 1:02, 1:01, 1:01 and 1:01 which reveal that the seat and table would cater for 30%, 20%, 50% and 100% staff of agricultural education programme in RSU, IAUOE and F.C.E. (T.), Omoku respectively. However, the analysis shows that in RSU, IAUOE, and F.C.E. (T.), Omoku, demonstration farm, domestic animal barns, laboratory, experiment tools, microscope, library space, book shelves, agricultural education encyclopedia, library reading tables, and staff room air-conditioner are not adequately provided as input resources for agricultural education hands-on-experience programme.

The table also shows that in RSU, IAUOE and F.C.E. (T.), Omoku, farm tools and tractors as input resources for agricultural education hands-on-experience are not adequately provided for with ratio of 1:05, 1:21, 1:04, 1:12, 1:85 and 1:34 which means each farm tool and each tractor would be used by 8%, 34%, 27%, 15%, 100% and 51% of the students respectively which is above ratio 1:3 provided by both NUC and NCCE BMAS. The table also shows that planting machine, harvesters, hitches machines, agricultural product drying machine, grinder and packaging tools are not provided for in IAUOE and F.C.E. (T.), Omoku as input resources for agricultural education programme hands-on-experiences; in RSU planting machine, harvesters, hitches machines, agricultural product drying machine, and grinder are not adequate. The analysis also shows that packaging tools are not available in RSU, IAUOE and F.C.E. (T.), Omoku for agricultural education hands-on experiences.

Table 2 also shows that all the consumables required as input resources for agricultural education programme hands-on-experiences are not available in RSU; while only domestic animals, animal feeds and birds are available in IAUOE at the ratio of 1:2, 1:85, and 1:3. This translates to the fact that domestic animals and birds are adequately available at 2% and 28% respectively; while in F.C.E. (T.), Omoku only birds are available at the ratio of 1:03 which means that it can be used for 50% of the students' hands-on-experience practical demonstration and task performance at once. The table also reveals that animal feeds provided in IAUOE are not adequate while other consumables are not available.

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference in the mean rating of agricultural educators from Rivers State University, Ignatius Ajuru University of Education and Federal College of Education (Tech.), Omoku on the adequacy of context of agricultural education for improved hands-on experience among students of Tertiary institutions in Rivers State.

Table 3: Summary of Analysis of Variance on significant difference in the mean rating of Agricultural Educators from RSU, IAUOE and F.C.E. (T.), Omoku on the adequacy of Context of Agricultural Education for Improved Hands-on Experience

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	.93	2	.46	.12	.89
Within Groups	78.70	21	3.75		
Total	79.63	23			

Table 3 shows between group sum of squares is 0.93, with 2 as degree of freedom and mean square of 0.46. The table also shows within group sum of squares is 78.70 and 21 degrees of freedom as well as mean square of 3.75. The total has 79.63 sum of squares and 23 degrees of freedom. The computed F ratio is 0.12 which is statistically significant alpha at 0.89. Therefore, the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference in the mean rating of agricultural educators from RSU, IAUOE and F.C.E. (T.), Omoku on the adequacy of context of agricultural education for improved Hands-on Experience among students in Tertiary Institutions, is accepted; $F(2, 21) = 0.12, p > 0.05$ at 0.89. This means there is no significant difference in the mean rating of agricultural educators on the adequacy of context of agricultural education for improved Hands-on experience among students in Tertiary institutions in Rivers State.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference in the adequacy of inputs necessary for implementing agricultural education hands-on experience among students of tertiary institutions in Rivers State.

Table 4: Summary of Analysis of Variance on significant difference in the mean rating of Agricultural Educators from RSU, IAUOE and F.C.E. (T.), Omoku on the adequacy of Context of Agricultural Education for Improved Hands-on Experience

	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	462.637	2	231.319	.154	.857
Within Groups	197711.911	132	1497.818		
Total	198174.548	134			

Table 4 shows between group sum of squares is 462.64, with 2 as degree of freedom and mean square of 231.319. The table also shows within group sum of squares is 197,711.91 and 132 degrees of freedom as well as mean square of 1497.818. The total has 198,174.55 sum of squares and 134 degrees of freedom. The computed F ratio is 0.15 which is statistically significant alpha at 0.86. Therefore, the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference in the adequacy of inputs necessary for implementing agricultural education hands-on experience among students of tertiary institutions in Rivers State, is accepted; $F(2, 132) = 0.15, p > 0.05$ at 0.86. This means there is no significant difference in the adequacy of inputs necessary for implementing agricultural education hands-on experience among students of tertiary institutions in Rivers State

Discussion of Major Findings

Determine the adequacy of context of agricultural education for improved hands-on experience among students of tertiary institutions in Rivers State.

The results related to this specific purpose show that lecturers from RSU, IAUOE and FCE(T), Omoku all agreed to the adequacy of the context of agricultural education for improved hands-on experience amongst students of tertiary

institutions in Rivers State. The results of test of hypothesis related to this specific purpose show that there is no significant difference in the mean rating of agricultural educators on the adequacy of context of agricultural education for improved Hands-on experience among students in Tertiary institutions in Rivers State. These findings emanated from the fact that lecturers from all the tertiary institutions in Rivers State agreed that the stated context upon which agricultural education programme is built which are to develop skills and have scientific knowledge and competencies required in agricultural sector; to develop the ability to secure satisfaction in the placement and advancement in agricultural occupation through programmes on continuing education; to develop leadership qualities, attitudes, thrifts scholarship co-operations, citizenship and patriotism by participating in experiences and activities of agricultural programmes; to develop competencies required by individuals engaged in agriculture; and to develop practical skills and competences in agricultural research can promote hands-on-experiences in agricultural education. The findings are contrary to the discovery of Amadi (2012) who found gap between what agricultural education programme curriculum offers to students at this level and what takes place in the actual agricultural world of work at this level. This connotes that the context is not adequate for developing students for the world of work. The findings of these studies are supported by the assertion of Francis et al., (2020) who noted that the framework of vocational agricultural education curriculum for productive work skills development adequate ensure the development of skills through exposure to agricultural experiences meant to empower graduates to engage in their own agricultural businesses and enable them develop skills for teaching others improved agricultural practices. The findings of the study are also supported by the finding of Ekezie and Owo (2019) who found that the stakeholders in agricultural education are of the view that the curriculum content at the university level is adequate enough to train students in vocational agricultural skills development. The findings are also supported by the finding of Ekele, Doom and Ngbongha (2020) when their study revealed that respondents rated all the programme course content appropriate

Determine the adequacy of inputs necessary for implementing agricultural education hands-on experience among students of tertiary institutions in Rivers State.

The results related to this specific purpose show that there are adequate human resources in agricultural education programme for improved hands-on-experiences in all tertiary institutions in Rivers State. The results also show that input resources such as instructional technology, infrastructure, equipment and consumables are either inadequate or not provided for agricultural education for improved hands-on experiences amongst students of tertiary institutions in Rivers State. The results of test of hypothesis relating to this specific purpose show that there is no significant difference in the adequacy of inputs necessary for implementing agricultural education hands-on experience among students of tertiary institutions in Rivers State. These findings emanated from the fact that it was discovered that technology, computer systems and multimedia projector are not adequately provided in RSU, IAUOE, and F.C.E. (T.), Omoku while access to internet and agricultural education software as input resource for agricultural education for improved hands-on experience is not available in the three tertiary institutions used for the study.

The results also emanated from the fact that it was discovered that there are adequate classrooms, staff offices, seat and table for staff offices in RSU, IAUOE and F.C.E. (T.), Omoku; while demonstration farm, domestic animal barns, laboratory, experiment tools, microscope, library space, book shelves, agricultural education encyclopedia, library reading tables, staff room air-conditioner, farm tools, and tractors are not adequately provided as input resources for agricultural education hands-on-experience programme. The findings also emanated because it was discovered that planting machine, harvesters, hatches machines, agricultural product drying machine, grinder and packaging tools are not provided for in IAUOE and F.C.E. (T.), Omoku as input resources for agricultural education programme hands-on-experiences; in RSU planting machine, harvesters, hatches machines, agricultural product drying machine, and grinder are not adequate. The findings also emanated from the fact that it was discovered that of all the consumables required as input resources for agricultural education programme hands-on-experiences only domestic animals, animal feeds and birds are available in IAUOE; while in F.C.E. (T.), Omoku only birds are available. In RSU, none of the consumables were available and funding for hands-on educational exercises are not provided in all the institutions evaluated. The findings of this study are supported by the findings of Ekezie and Owo (2019) who reported that the stakeholders in agricultural education are of the view that lecturers provided for the implementation of agricultural education curriculum at the university level are adequately available to train students in vocational agricultural skills

development. Ekezie and Owo also found that the stakeholders in agricultural education are of the view that the environment and facilities needed for the implementation of agricultural education curriculum at the university level are inadequate for vocational agricultural skills development amongst students. The findings of the study are also supported by the finding of Ekele, Doom and Ngbongha (2020) when they reported that their checklist showed that most of the facilities needed for implementing agricultural education programme were moderately available.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the findings of this study, it is concluded that the context of agricultural education curriculum is adequate for improved hands-on experiences among students of tertiary institutions in Rivers State. It can also be concluded that apart from human resources, all other inputs resources such as instructional technology, infrastructure, equipment and consumables are either inadequate in ratio of number to anticipated users or not provided for agricultural education improved hands-on experiences amongst students of tertiary institutions in Rivers State.

Recommendations

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, conclusions made and the implications, the following recommendations were posed:

1. The Federal and Rivers State ministry education should revisit the context of agricultural education in order improve it for better hands-on experience capable of empowering students with competencies for 21st century agricultural practices.
2. Federal and Rivers State government should provide more funding for the provision of adequate and functional input resources relating to instructional technology, infrastructure, equipment and consumables for agricultural education hands-on experiences amongst students of tertiary institutions in Rivers State.

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